
Semi-supervised Amharic Sentiment classification

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Abstract

To properly apply supervised machine learning, sufficient labeled corpus is required. In this study, we proposed a semi-supervised approach to Amharic sentiment classification. As Amharic is less-resourced language, there is insufficient labeled corpus to apply supervised machine learning. Nowadays, Amharic texts are widely used in social media, which invites for the development of machine-learning based applications. We applied Naive Bayesian with expectation maximization(NB-EM) under insufficient Amharic sentiment labeled datasets with minimal annotation costs in faster development time. With 5 cross-fold validation, we tested NB-EM for Amharic sentiment classification and achieved an accuracy of 83% with partially unlabeled corpus. We also investigated the proposed approach with varying training size and showing progressive improvement on performance of Sentiment classification. The approach can be adopted to other less-resourced languages to remedy the shortage of labeled corpus.

1 Introduction

In general, semi-supervised /transfer learning is grouped into (a) inductive learning that learns from both labeled and unlabeled data and (b) transductive learning that learns from both labeled and unlabeled data. Unlike inductive learning, transductive learning doesn't predict unseen data which is not seen during training. Most graph-based algorithms are transductive learning. Semi-supervised is divided into four groups where each algorithm differs from each other by the assumptions it is using. a) Iterative (e.g. expectation-maximization, self-learning), (b) margin-based models(e.g. TSVM) (c) graph-based models and (d) committee-based models(e.g. co-training and co-forest) [4, 6]. In this study, we proposed Naive Bayesian with expectation-maximization. A similar work has been carried out using Naive Bayesian for semi-supervised fashion with slight variation in [1, 5, 3, 2]. In this study, we used char ngram language model using tfidf as a feature set for the proposed approach. **Contributions:**The key contributions of this research are (i) char ngram with tfidf is outperformed for partially labeled dataset as compared with word-level feature, (ii) semi-supervised with NB-EM is developed for sentiment classification under insufficient labeled corpus, (iii) the approach is cost-effective in-terms of processing time and the manual efforts for annotation, and (iv) the developed approach can be replicated for other less-resourced languages.

2 The Proposed Approach

The proposed semi-supervised Naive Bayes with Expectation-Maximization approach has two main steps to accomplish its task: prediction of unlabeled sample and re-estimation of the NB classifier parameter using labeled sample. These steps are repeated while the classifier is improved and all unlabeled samples are optimally predicted. The key steps of the semi-supervised approach(i.e.NB

using EM) is briefly presented in the listing 1.

Algorithm 1: Proposed semi-supervised with NB with EM

Input: Dataset: D contains both labeled and unlabeled data Training and Test sets.

Output: Final fitted NB with EM model that returns prediction of class of unlabeled sample.

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1 foreach  $k \in CV=5$  do
2   Build an initial NB classifier  $\theta$  using labeled training sets by using max. posterior
   estimation(i.e.  $\theta = \operatorname{argmax}(P(D|\theta)P(\theta))$ )
3   while classifier,  $\theta$  improves: do
4     Pick N samples from Training set.
5     Predict class of the  $i^{th} \in N$  unlabeled sample using the current classifier,  $\theta$  (i.e.
      $P(c_i|d_i, \theta)$ ).
6     Re-estimate the classifier parameters,  $\theta$ , with those predicted subset samples.
7 Compute average accuracy of all k fold iterations.

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3 Experiment, Results and Discussion

We adopted the approach in [2] and implemented in python library. We used PMO Facebook datasets(6652 samples) with 5CV and vectorized into char level tfidf with ngrams of size 7 and maximum number of features of 5000). Of the total dataset, only 20% of the data(without label) is randomly taken for NB-EM. To test the progressive improvement of the proposed approach, we split this data into 20 training sizes(199,236,280,...,5011). For each training size, the 5CV score of the approach is returned. The 5CV scores for these training sizes is improved from 74% to 83%. Our approach of semi-supervised outperformed the performance of NB with out EM(baseline). The performance of this semi-supervised method with 5-folds cross-validation. These result revealed that as training size increases, performance of our proposed NB with EM is also increase in accuracy. The performance of NB with EM and NB alone in relation to training size is visualized in the plot displayed in figure 1.

Figure 1: NB vs NB-EM performance comparison by training sizes

Using test set, the performance of NB with EM is a little bit better than NB till training size of 2000. Between a training size of 2000 and 3000, the performance of NB classifier is getting better than NB with EM. Above training size of 3000, the performance of both Semi-NB EM and NB classifier gets flattened and flattened without significant improvement of performance even though the training size gets larger and larger. We also evaluated by interpreting the top 3 positive and 3 negative features obtained from trained EM-NB classifier(i.e. positive:ጅግና, ጠቅላይ, አብይ/Our hero PM Abiy Ahmed/ and the negative:አትፍሩ, አልታየም, አልታወቀም /let you not frighten, He was not seen, He was not known/).

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